

1 **Title:** Endometriosis and irritable bowel syndrome: similarities and differences in the
2 spectrum of comorbidities

3

4 **Running title:** Comorbidities of endometriosis and IBS

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23 **Abstract**

24 **Study question:** Do the spectrum and prevalence of comorbidities of endometriosis and
25 irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) overlap?

26 **Summary answer:** Despite several overlapping symptoms, the most significantly associated
27 comorbidities of endometriosis and IBS are different and rather related to the organ systems
28 primarily involved in the index diagnosis.

29 **What is known already:** Endometriosis and IBS both have several similar unspecific
30 symptoms, such as recurrent abdominal pain, cramping and anxiety, and both diseases affect
31 young women and are associated with a number of comorbidities causing a poor quality of
32 life. A detailed study, revealing the full spectrum of endometriosis and IBS comorbidities in
33 the same study population, is lacking.

34 **Study design, size, duration:** A retrospective *in silico* analysis of the data from a large
35 nationwide biobank-based cohort consisting of 121,773 women. After excluding all first- and
36 second-degree relatives, the data of up to 65,421 women was analyzed.

37 **Participants/materials, setting, methods:** International Classification of Disease-10
38 diagnosis main codes associated with endometriosis (N80) and IBS (K58) diagnoses were
39 identified from the Estonian Biobank dataset by linking with the Estonian Health Insurance
40 Fund and other relevant registries. The associations between N80 and K58 and other
41 diagnosis codes were tested using logistic regression, adjusting for age at recruitment, and ten
42 genetic principal components to account for potential population stratification. Bonferroni
43 correction was applied to account for multiple testing.

44 **Main results and the role of chance:** Both women with endometriosis and IBS suffered
45 from more conditions compared to the control group, with 226 and 428 diagnosis codes
46 statistically significantly more frequent in women with respective diagnosis compared to

47 controls. Women suffering from both conditions had 275 significantly associated
48 comorbidities. A remarkable proportion of women with IBS and endometriosis suffered also
49 from endometriosis (9.4%) or IBS (14.3%), respectively. In endometriosis, the most prevalent
50 diagnoses were related to diseases of the genitourinary system (33 N-category codes) and in
51 women with IBS, the most associated diagnoses were related to digestive disorders and
52 gastrointestinal tract (52 codes from K-category). Among the most significant diagnoses in
53 endometriosis were uterine leiomyomas (D25), menstrual disorders (N92) and infertility
54 (N97) ($P < 1 \times 10^{-315}$ for all), and in IBS, lactose intolerance (E73), gastritis and duodenitis
55 (K29) and functional dyspepsia (K30) were in the top list of most significant comorbidities (P
56 $< 1 \times 10^{-315}$ for all).

57 **Limitations, reasons for caution:** The information about the severity stages of endometriosis
58 and subtypes of IBS was not available for analysis. The findings may not be fully extrapolated
59 to all female populations, because all participants were from one geographic area, and had
60 good access to health services.

61 **Wider implications of the findings:** These findings support previous studies that have found
62 a high prevalence of pre-selected comorbidities in women with endometriosis and IBS.
63 However, taking into account the differences in the full spectrum of comorbidities of
64 endometriosis and IBS may aid in diagnosing these disorders. Women and healthcare
65 providers need to be aware that women with endometriosis are at high risks of complications
66 during pregnancy and should be carefully monitored.

67 **Study funding/competing interest(s):**

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74

75 **Keywords:** comorbidity, diagnosis codes, endometriosis, gastrointestinal tract, genitourinary
76 system, ICD-10, impaired life quality, irritable bowel syndrome, pregnancy complications

77

78 **Introduction**

79 Endometriosis is a complex and heterogeneous disease that worsens the life quality of many
80 women (Nnoaham *et al.*, 2019). The prevalence of endometriosis ranges between 1 and 5%
81 (Sarria-Santamera *et al.*, 2021), however, it is difficult to assess the exact frequency as there
82 are no specific symptoms or non-invasive diagnostic biomarkers, also the estimates depend on
83 the particular study design, source of information, and case definition. Endometriosis
84 phenotypes are heterogeneous, and symptoms include pelvic pain, infertility, and anxiety.
85 Endometriosis may correlate with many coexisting disorders relating to multiple organ
86 systems (Zondervan *et al.*, 2020). The presence of comorbidities with overlapping symptoms
87 makes the diagnosis even more difficult. Several studies have focused on the various
88 comorbidities of endometriosis and association with different cancers has been found (Wang
89 *et al.*, 2016; Kvaskoff *et al.*, 2021). High incidence of coexisting gynecologic conditions, such
90 as uterine leiomyomas and endometriosis has been reported (Choi *et al.*, 2017; Lin *et al.*,
91 2021) and women with endometriosis may have an increased risk of premature birth
92 (Bonuccelli *et al.*, 2021). However, no large-scale studies have estimated the prevalence of
93 unselected diagnosis codes co-occurring with endometriosis.

94 Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) similarly has unspecific symptoms (recurrent abdominal pain,
95 constipation, cramping), lacks non-invasive diagnostic markers and associates with a poor life
96 quality (Ford *et al.*, 2020). The prevalence of IBS is around 10% on average (Lovell and Ford,
97 2012); however, introduction of the latest Rome IV criteria has led to a decrease in IBS
98 prevalence (Vork *et al.*, 2018). IBS affects slightly more young adult women than men
99 (Lovell and Ford, 2012). Patients with IBS frequently suffer from psychological comorbidities
100 (Goodoory *et al.*, 2021; Staudacher *et al.*, 2021) and coexistence of IBS and fibromyalgia is
101 common (Erdrich *et al.*, 2020). A recent large survey-based population study revealed that
102 IBS was associated with mental disorders, increased odds of headache, chronic pain, diabetes

103 mellitus and sleep disorders (Grover *et al.*, 2021). The higher co-existence of mental health,
104 pain-related, and other functional comorbidities among IBS patients was confirmed in a large
105 cross-sectional cohort study using data from a national managed care database (Beinvogl *et*
106 *al.*, 2021). Recent meta-analysis revealed at least two-fold risk of IBS in women with
107 endometriosis compared to women without the disease, and because of overlapping
108 symptoms, misdiagnosis between the two conditions is likely (Chiaffarino *et al.*, 2021).

109 We hypothesized that as endometriosis and IBS share several features, both conditions may
110 have common comorbidities. Therefore, the aim of the current study was to use a large
111 population-based biobank dataset of 121,773 women from the Estonian Biobank (EstBB),
112 (Leitsalu *et al.*, 2015b) whose health status is characterized by continuously updated
113 International Classification of Disease-10 (ICD-10) codes from various sources, to compare
114 comorbidities in women with endometriosis, women from the general population, and women
115 with IBS.

116

117 **Methods**

118 *Study cohort*

119 EstBB is a population-based biobank with health information for over 200,000 participants in
120 the latest data freeze (Leitsalu *et al.*, 2015b). Information on ICD-10 codes is obtained via
121 regular linking with the Estonian Health Insurance Fund (EHIF) and other relevant registries,
122 such as Estonian National Health Information System, Estonian Cancer Registry and others
123 (Leitsalu *et al.*, 2015a). Electronic data is available starting from year 1993, with majority of
124 data originating from 2003 and onwards, meaning that for older biobank participants, the
125 electronic diagnosis data is not as complete. However, biobank participants have filled out a

126 questionnaire with additional information on diagnoses. All female biobank participants were
127 included in the analysis.

128 *Ethical approval*

129 All biobank participants have signed a broad informed consent form and the study was carried
130 out under ethical approval 1.1-12/624 (March 24, 2020) from the Estonian Committee on
131 Bioethics and Human Research (Estonian Ministry of Social Affairs) and data release N05
132 from the EstBB.

133 *Statistical analysis*

134 Using the individual level data in the EstBB, we conducted an analysis to find ICD-10
135 diagnosis main codes associated with the ICD-10 N80 (endometriosis) and K58 (IBS)
136 diagnoses. We tested the associations between N80 and K58 and other ICD-10 codes using
137 logistic regression, adjusting for age at recruitment, and ten genetic principal components to
138 account for potential population stratification and avoid false associations because of
139 ancestry/regional differences of cases and controls. Age was included as a covariate to
140 account for the fact that for older biobank participants, the electronic diagnosis data may not
141 be as complete. We restricted our analysis to diagnosis main codes including all subcodes to
142 reduce the granularity of the data and increase power. Bonferroni correction was applied to
143 select statistically significant associations (Number of tested ICD main codes—2000,
144 corrected P-value threshold — 2.5×10^{-5}). Odds ratios (OR) are calculated based on logistic
145 regression and thus represent adjusted ORs. We filtered the results to remove diagnoses
146 mainly related to exogeneous factors (injuries, poisoning, accidents, assaults etc. in S, T, U,
147 V, W, X, Y subchapters). Results were visualized using the PheWAS library
148 (<https://github.com/PheWAS/PheWAS>). All analyses were carried out in R 3.6.1.

149

150 **Results**

151 *Study population*

152 In the EstBB, data of 121,773 women were available for analyses. Individuals with
153 endometriosis and IBS were identified using the ICD-10 codes N80 and K58, respectively,
154 resulting in 7,142 endometriosis (prevalence 5.9%) and 10,781 IBS cases (prevalence 8.9%).
155 Among the women with endometriosis or IBS, the prevalence of the other investigated
156 disorder was higher than in the entire study cohort (the prevalence of IBS was 13.6% among
157 endometriosis cases and the prevalence of endometriosis was 9.0% among individuals with
158 IBS). However, for the comorbidity analysis of endometriosis and IBS, individuals with K58
159 and/or N80 diagnosis codes were excluded from the cohort of controls (Supplementary Figure
160 S1). Further, the EstBB includes a remarkable number of relatives (the 200K data freeze
161 represents ~20% of the entire Estonian adult population) and as both diseases are complex
162 polygenic conditions with possible heritable component (Henström and D'Amato, 2016;
163 Zondervan *et al.*, 2020), inclusion of relatives might inflate the association statistics.
164 Therefore, all first- and second-degree relatives (cut-off pi-hat value 0.2) were excluded in
165 pairwise comparisons, keeping the index cases, if possible, to not lose in power (in case of
166 both relatives suffering from endometriosis or IBS, one index case was still excluded). After
167 filtering for relatives, data of up to 65,421 women remained for analysis. In this subset, 5,972
168 and 9,266 women had ICD-10 diagnosis codes N80 and K58, respectively, while 966 women
169 suffered from both diagnoses (Table I). All ICD-10 codes with significantly higher prevalence
170 among women with endometriosis, IBS and both diagnosis compared to controls are given in
171 Supplementary Tables SI to SIII. Unfortunately, as information on endometriosis severity
172 (mild or severe) or IBS subgroups (the predominant bowel habits) is not available in the
173 EstBB database, we were unable to perform further subgroup-based analysis.

174 According to our analysis, women with IBS had considerably more accompanying diagnoses
175 compared to individuals with endometriosis (428 and 226 ICD codes, respectively, were
176 statistically significantly more frequent in women with IBS and endometriosis compared to
177 controls). Women suffering from both diseases had 275 significantly associated comorbidities
178 (Figure 1).

179 *Comorbidities of endometriosis*

180 As expected, the most significant diagnoses in endometriosis were related to infertility,
181 reproductive organs, and gynecological disorders (Table II). Also, diagnoses reflecting known
182 symptoms of endometriosis, such as menstrual disorders, pelvic pain and infertility were in
183 the top list of endometriosis comorbidities. The first diagnosis unrelated to endometriosis
184 symptoms or gynecological conditions was iron deficiency anemia (ICD-10 code D50),
185 prevalence among women with and without endometriosis 35.9% and 23.2% (OR 1.9, 95% CI
186 1.8-1.9), respectively. Diseases of the genitourinary system (33 codes belonging to N-
187 category) were most prevalent, followed by diseases of the musculoskeletal system (30 codes
188 from M-category). Twenty-one codes were related to factors influencing health status and
189 contact with health services (Z-category). Sixteen O-category codes, relating to pregnancy,
190 childbirth and the puerperium were statistically significant (Supplementary Figure S2),
191 including ectopic pregnancy (O00, OR 2.0, 95% CI 1.8-2.1), spontaneous abortions (O03, OR
192 1.7, 95% CI 1.6-1.8), and preterm labor and delivery (O60, OR 1.8, 95% CI 1.6-1.9). Multiple
193 gestation (O30) and multiple delivery (O84) were also significantly more common among
194 women with endometriosis compared to controls (2.4% vs 1.0% and 1.7% vs 0.6%,
195 respectively), most probably due to the significantly higher use of procreative management
196 (Z31) by women with endometriosis (13.2% in endometriosis vs 3.3% in controls, $P= 1.1 \times$
197 10^{-274}). The analysis revealed also overrepresentation of malignant neoplasm of ovary (C56)
198 and of corpus uteri (C54) in women with endometriosis (frequency: 0.8% endometriosis,

199 0.4% controls, OR 2.2, 95% CI 1.9-2.5, $P= 1.5 \times 10^{-6}$ for C56 and frequency 0.7%
200 endometriosis, 0.6% controls, OR 2.1, 95% CI 1.7-2.4, $P= 2.3 \times 10^{-5}$ for C54). In addition,
201 among other neoplasm categories (D-category codes D00-D48), 12 diagnosis codes were
202 significantly more common in endometriosis group (e.g. D22, Melanocytic naevi, OR 1.4,
203 95% CI 1.4-1.5, $P= 3.4 \times 10^{-30}$).

204 There were also two diagnosis codes significantly overrepresented among women without
205 endometriosis compared to women with endometriosis. Both are diseases of oral cavity,
206 salivary glands and jaws, with dental caries (K02) being almost twice as common in controls
207 (27.5% vs 15.3% in cases). However, this finding should be considered with caution as EHIF
208 reimburses dental care to adults only to a limited extent and this might lead to incomplete
209 data.

210 *Comorbidities of IBS*

211 In women with IBS, the most significantly associated diagnoses were related to digestive
212 disorders and gastrointestinal tract, such as gastro-oesophageal reflux disease, functional
213 dyspepsia, and gastritis and duodenitis (Table III). The difference in the prevalence of lactose
214 intolerance (E73) was almost sevenfold among women with and without IBS diagnosis
215 (11.3% and 1.6%, respectively, OR 8.5, 95% CI 8.4-8.6). Further, diagnoses related to mental
216 health, such as somatoform disorders (F45), anxiety disorders (F41), and depression episode
217 (F32) were among the comorbidities most significantly associated with IBS. When viewing
218 the IBS comorbidities' codes by categories, the most represented categories were diseases of
219 the digestive system (52 K-category codes) and diseases of the musculoskeletal system and
220 connective tissue (48 M-category codes). The next enriched comorbidity categories among
221 women with IBS were related to symptoms, signs and abnormal clinical and laboratory
222 findings (41 R-category codes) and diseases of the genitourinary system (35 N-category
223 codes). Two digestive tract malignant neoplasms were more prevalent in women with IBS

224 compared to controls [malignant neoplasm of colon (C18, OR 2.3, 95% CI 2.1-2.5) and
225 malignant neoplasm of rectum (C20, OR 2.3, 95% CI 2.0-2.7)], but the frequencies of both
226 conditions were rather low (1.4% and 0.5% among women with IBS and 0.5% and 0.2%
227 among controls, respectively). However, of the category D codes D00-D48, 18 were
228 represented as comorbidities of IBS (e.g. D12 Benign neoplasm of colon, rectum, anus and
229 anal canal, OR 4.3, 95% CI 4.2-4.4).

230 *Comorbidities in women with both endometriosis and IBS*

231 Among study cohort women, 996 individuals had both diagnoses. In this group, ten out of 20
232 top-list comorbidities were diseases of the genitourinary system, but the first two most
233 significantly associated diagnosis (leiomyoma of uterus and lactose intolerance) overlapped
234 with the top comorbidities of endometriosis and IBS, respectively (Table IV). However, the
235 most represented categories in the entire list of comorbidities in this group of women were
236 diseases of the digestive system (36 K-category codes), diseases of the musculoskeletal
237 system and connective tissue (M-category), and diseases of the genitourinary system (N-
238 category), both with 32 codes. The risk of several comorbid diagnoses was higher in this
239 group of women compared to women having only one index diagnosis, with the most
240 remarkably increased risk for abdominal and pelvic pain (R10): from OR 1.7 (95% CI 1.7-
241 1.8) and OR 3.1 (95% CI 3.1-3.2) in endometriosis and IBS, respectively to OR 5.6 (95% CI
242 5.5-5.8) in women with both diagnoses.

243 *Overlap of diagnostic codes in the study groups*

244 When we compared endometriosis and IBS comorbidities, 181 ICD-10 codes were common
245 in both groups (i.e., 80.1% and 42.3% of all endometriosis and IBS comorbidities,
246 respectively); furthermore, 161 out of these 181 diagnoses were represented also in women
247 suffering from both endometriosis and IBS (Supplementary Table SIV, Supplementary Figure

248 S3). However, if we compared the top 20 most significantly associated comorbidities of
249 endometriosis and IBS, only two diagnoses overlapped: abdominal and pelvic pain (R10) and
250 menopausal and other perimenopausal disorders (N95). Thirty diagnoses were specific to
251 endometriosis, 156 codes were related only to IBS and eight codes were specific to women
252 having both diagnoses. Seven out of these eight codes had frequency less than 2% in both
253 controls and cases, and only excessive vomiting in pregnancy (O21) reached 5% among cases
254 (2.6% in controls, OR 2.4, 95% CI 2.1-2.7). Twelve out of 30 endometriosis-specific
255 comorbidities were associated with pregnancy and childbirth complications (O-category).
256 Among the diagnoses for IBS alone, none of the categories prevailed, but rather reflected
257 general IBS comorbidities.

258

259 **Discussion**

260 According to our knowledge, the current study including all available ICD-10 codes, is the
261 most comprehensive comorbidity study of endometriosis and IBS to date. We found that both
262 women with endometriosis and IBS suffered from more conditions compared to the control
263 group. However, despite the symptomatic similarities between these two conditions, the most
264 significantly associated comorbidities were related to the anatomical location and nature of
265 the disease, with diseases of the genitourinary system, and digestive and gastrointestinal tract
266 being the most prevalent in endometriosis and IBS, respectively.

267 We confirmed a higher incidence of IBS in women with endometriosis compared to controls,
268 and found a higher prevalence of endometriosis in individuals with IBS compared to those
269 without the disease. The higher risk of IBS in endometriosis has been reported previously
270 (Seaman *et al.*, 2008; Ek *et al.*, 2018; Schomacker *et al.*, 2018), but only one study has
271 described a significantly higher incidence of endometriosis in the IBS population (Moore *et*

272 *al.*, 2017). The reported prevalence of endometriosis in women with and without IBS was
273 remarkably higher (37% in IBS vs 15% without IBS) than what we found (9.0% in IBS vs
274 5.9% without IBS), explainable by the differences in the study cohorts. Most of female
275 patients enrolled to the study by Moore *et al.* (2017) suffered from pelvic pain and bowel
276 symptoms affected by menstruation, and therefore, a higher than usual incidence of
277 endometriosis was likely in this group (Moore *et al.*, 2017).

278 Endometriosis impairs the life quality and work productivity of many affected women
279 (Nnoaham *et al.*, 2019), with pelvic pain mainly driving the productivity loss. Pelvic pain is
280 one of the most common symptoms of endometriosis that is probably closely related to central
281 sensitization (Zheng *et al.*, 2019). Abdominal and pelvic pain were among the most frequent
282 comorbidities in both our endometriosis and IBS groups; however, women suffering from
283 both diagnoses had the most abdominal pain: 74.9% vs 60.7% and 47.9% in endometriosis
284 and IBS, respectively. In addition, genital organs and menstrual cycle-related pain was almost
285 twice as common in endometriosis as in controls (22.6% vs 12.4 %). Gonalong-releasing
286 hormone agonists (GnRHa) are suggested as one of the options to reduce endometriosis-
287 associated pain if combined hormonal contraceptives or progestogens have been ineffective
288 (Group *et al.*, 2022). GnRHa treatment has also been shown to significantly improve the
289 bowel symptoms in IBS (Mathias *et al.*, 1994; Palomba *et al.*, 2005). However, GnRHa
290 treatment may also exacerbate endometriosis patients' gastrointestinal symptoms e.g.,
291 abdominal pain (Ek *et al.*, 2015).

292 Severe pain symptoms and complaints may lead to more medical visits (particularly to
293 obstetrician–gynecologists) and examinations, during which more comorbidities may be
294 revealed. The most significantly associated comorbidity of endometriosis in our study, uterine
295 leiomyoma shares many common clinical features with endometriosis, including pelvic pain
296 and infertility, and both may be diagnosed when looking for the causes of these complaints.

297 The frequent co-existence of leiomyoma and endometriosis has been described before (Surrey
298 *et al.*, 2018; Lin *et al.*, 2021) and leiomyoma could potentially predispose to retroverted
299 uterus or distort the uterine cavity, thereby increasing the risk of retrograde menstruation
300 leading to development of endometriosis (Lin *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, endometriosis and
301 leiomyoma share common genetic origins (Gallagher *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand it has
302 been found that the presence of more pelvic symptoms is related to delayed diagnosis
303 (Nnoaham *et al.*, 2019), because pain complaints are nonspecific and present a challenge for
304 physicians trying to identify the source of pain.

305 We found that a remarkable number of endometriosis-associated comorbidities were related to
306 pregnancy and childbirth, consistent with previous findings. A significantly higher relative
307 risk of preterm birth has been demonstrated in women with endometriosis (Bonuccelli *et al.*,
308 2021). The risk of miscarriage was increased in women with endometriosis compared to
309 controls in case of spontaneous pregnancy, but not among women who used infertility
310 treatment (Huang *et al.*, 2020) and some studies (Hjordt Hansen *et al.*, 2014; Saraswat *et al.*,
311 2017) have detected approximately a two-fold higher risk for ectopic pregnancy in women
312 with endometriosis. Furthermore, a recent meta-analysis confirmed an association between
313 endometriosis and several adverse pregnancy outcomes (Breintoft *et al.*, 2021). All this
314 suggests that women with endometriosis should be warned about the risks of complications
315 during pregnancy and carefully monitored.

316 The relationship between endometriosis and ovarian cancer has been extensively investigated,
317 both on epidemiological and genetic level (Lee *et al.*, 2016), and the prevailing position is that
318 although ovarian cancer will develop in only a small subset (0.3–1.6%) of women with
319 endometriosis, the risk might be two or three times higher than in controls (Guidozzi, 2021).
320 Our results are consistent with this conclusion, both in terms of ovarian cancer frequency
321 among women with endometriosis (0.8%) and observed OR rate (2.2, 95% CI 1.9-2.5). The

322 relationship between endometriosis and endometrial cancer risk is still unclear. A recent meta-
323 analysis showed no association between endometriosis and endometrial cancer risk, but also
324 stressed the high between-studies heterogeneity (Kvaskoff *et al.*, 2021). On the opposite, a
325 large population-based retrospective cohort study revealed significantly increased incidence
326 of endometrial cancer in women with histologically proven endometriosis (Hermens *et al.*,
327 2021). Interestingly, women with endometrial cancer and histologically proven endometriosis
328 have a better overall survival when compared to women with endometrial cancer without
329 endometriosis (Hermens *et al.*, 2022). In our cohort, women with endometriosis showed only
330 slightly higher incident of endometrial cancer compared to controls (0.7% vs. 0.6%,
331 respectively), but the difference was statistically significant.

332 One of the most significantly associated comorbidities of IBS was lactose intolerance. It is
333 noteworthy that if women had additionally the diagnosis of endometriosis, the risk of having
334 lactose intolerance was higher compared to the women having only IBS [OR 10.3 (95% CI
335 10.1-10.5) and OR 8.5 (95% CI 8.4-8.6) in women with both diseases vs. women with only
336 IBS, respectively], indicating that having both diagnoses may raise the risk of getting disease-
337 related comorbidities. The complaints of lactose or milk intolerance are common in IBS;
338 however, IBS symptoms are probably independent of lactose maldigestion as avoidance of
339 lactose does not lead to clinical improvement in IBS patients (Cancarevic *et al.*, 2020).
340 However, some studies have reported improvement of IBS severity after low-lactose diet
341 (Catanzaro *et al.*, 2020; Krieger-Grübel *et al.*, 2020), showing that more studies are needed to
342 elucidate the true association between IBS and lactose intolerance.

343 It has been shown that IBS patients have significantly more mental health, pain-related and
344 other functional comorbidities (Beinvogl *et al.*, 2021; Grover *et al.*, 2021), supported by a
345 strong genetic correlation between IBS, anxiety, neuroticism, and depression (Eijsbouts *et al.*,
346 2021). Our results are in line with the mentioned studies, with somatoform disorders, anxiety

347 and depression being more common in IBS patients. The mentioned mental health associated
348 comorbidities were also over-represented in our endometriosis cohort, corroborating the
349 previously shown high prevalence of depression and anxiety disorders in endometriosis
350 patients (reviewed in (Maulitz *et al.*, 2022)). In addition, a recent large observational study
351 reported that more than half of endometriosis patients reported feeling down and depressed
352 (Becker *et al.*, 2021). As endometriosis related pain correlates with the prevalence of
353 depression (Warzecha *et al.*, 2020), it may be one of the main triggers for mental health issues
354 in patients with endometriosis.

355 We noticed also significant association of IBS with headaches and migraine, a phenomenon
356 that has been described earlier (Lau *et al.*, 2014; Lankarani *et al.*, 2017; Kawashima *et al.*,
357 2020) and it has been proposed that these conditions may coexist within the spectrum of a
358 specific pain centralized disorder (Chang and Lu, 2013). Another hypothesis suggests
359 involvement of a gut-brain axis as both conditions alter the gut microflora composition and
360 inflammatory status (Arzani *et al.*, 2020). Even fecal microbiota transplantation has been tried
361 as a treatment and it appears to be a promising further approach alleviating IBS symptoms
362 (El-Salhy *et al.*, 2021).

363 Somewhat surprising was the association between IBS and upper respiratory infections (J31).
364 Respiratory and laryngopharyngeal diseases are frequent comorbidities of gastroesophageal
365 reflux disease (Wang *et al.*, 2004), which was very strongly associated with IBS in our study.
366 Gastroesophageal reflux disease and IBS are common conditions in the general population
367 with overlapping symptoms (Rasmussen *et al.*, 2015) and we can assume that the relationship
368 between IBS and J31 diseases is rather indirect through the association with another co-
369 morbidity.

370 Our results revealed that women with IBS had two times higher risk of colon and rectal
371 cancer compared to controls. The association between IBS and cancer is contradictory. Some

372 studies have shown that IBS is related to increased risk for colorectal neoplasms (Chang *et al.*,
373 2015) and others have found that even if immediately after an IBS diagnosis colon cancer
374 incidence rate was elevated, IBS was not associated with the long-term development of
375 neither colorectal nor rectal cancer (Nørgaard *et al.*, 2011; Hsiao *et al.*, 2014; Chang *et al.*,
376 2015), suggesting diagnostic confusion because of overlapping symptoms.

377 A major strength of this study was the inclusion of data from a large population-based
378 biobank, where data on diagnoses is obtained from different registries and constantly updated.
379 The diagnosis data mainly comes from EHIF and as Estonia has a solidary health insurance
380 system and national public health insurance covers approximately 95% of the population, the
381 available data are comprehensive and cover the entire study cohort.

382 The limitation is that the registers do not provide all relevant information that may affect the
383 incidence of comorbidities, e.g., neither the severity stages of endometriosis nor subgroups of
384 IBS can be distinguished. There are several classification systems for endometriosis staging
385 but as it was recently concluded, none of the existing classification systems predicts the
386 degree of pelvic pain, the disease recurrence, the risk of comorbidities and quality of life
387 (Capezzuoli *et al.*, 2020; AAGL *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, we assume that the results of the
388 current analysis for endometriosis comorbidities are not considerably affected by the lack of
389 staging information. However, the incidence of infertility shows a negative correlation with
390 endometriosis stages (D'Hooghe *et al.*, 2003; Warzecha *et al.*, 2020), and if we had the
391 information on the stages, we would probably have seen differences between the severity
392 stages. In case of IBS, subtypes are not always very clear and patients alternate between
393 subtypes over time (Engsbro *et al.*, 2012) resulting in a very large proportion of subjects being
394 defined as unclassified IBS (Simren *et al.*, 2017), which complicates subtype analysis. Also,
395 the lack of data did not allow to consider the effects of medical or surgical treatment on the
396 incidence of co-morbidities, and as the dates of the first diagnoses for all women and

397 diagnoses are not available, the analysis of the temporal sequence of the pathologies was not
398 possible. Further, voluntary biobank participants may represent a non-random sample,
399 including more health-conscious people interested in participating in research studies and be
400 healthier compared to the general population (Fry *et al.*, 2017), as individuals with a
401 debilitating diagnosis are unlikely to join. However, as the individuals in both the disease and
402 control group are from the same source, this should not affect the overall result. Finally, we
403 cannot exclude that some of the women in our control group have asymptomatic
404 endometriosis as the disease diagnosis is complicated and needs invasive laparoscopic
405 surgery. For example, incidental endometriosis has been detected even in 7% of women
406 suffering from polycystic ovary syndrome (Hager *et al.*, 2019), however, there is a lack of
407 knowledge on how asymptomatic endometriosis is associated to clinical outcomes.

408 In conclusion, our study provides information on which comorbidities are diagnosed in
409 women who suffer from endometriosis or/and IBS and shows that both diseases are associated
410 with many life-quality impairing conditions. It also highlights the fact that despite several
411 common symptoms, the most significantly associated comorbidities of these conditions are
412 different and rather related to the organ systems primarily involved in the index diagnosis.
413 Because of the overlapping symptoms in women of reproductive age, it may be difficult to
414 distinguish between endometriosis and IBS, which may lead to delayed diagnosis. Therefore,
415 wider awareness of the spectrum of the most common comorbidities may help to diagnose
416 these disorders. However, further research is needed to elucidate whether the comorbidities of
417 endometriosis and IBS differ between the disease stages and subtypes, respectively.

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421 Authors' roles

422 MP and TL were involved in the conception and design of the study. TL performed the
423 statistical analyses. MP and TL wrote the first draft and IM, HK, AS and RM contributed to
424 the interpretation of the results and revised the paper. All authors approved the final
425 manuscript.

426

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433

434 Conflict of interest

435 The authors do not have any competing interests to declare.

436

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440 Biobank data were performed in the High Performance Computing Center, University of
441 Tartu.

442

443 **Data availability**

444 The data underlying this article are available in the article and in its online supplementary
445 material.

446

447 **References**

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638 Table I. Descriptive characteristics of study groups.

Characteristic	Endometriosis		IBS		Both	
	Cases	Controls	Cases	Controls	Cases	Controls
n	5,972	57,125	9,266	56,155	966	58,564
Age at recruitment (years)	44.4 (10.9)	44.7 (15.9)	48.6 (16.9)	44.4 (15.9)	45.9 (11.3)	44.4 (15.9)
Age at menarche (years)	13.3 (1.4)	13.4 (1.5)	13.4 (1.5)	13.4 (1.5)	13.2 (1.4)	13.4 (1.5)
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	25.9 (5.4)	25.8 (5.5)	25.8 (5.5)	25.8 (5.4)	25.5 (5.2)	25.8 (5.5)

639 All values are shown as mean (standard deviation). IBS, irritable bowel syndrome

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643 Table II. The list of 20 most significant comorbidities of endometriosis cases compared with controls.

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ICD-10 code	Comorbidity	Endometriosis n (%)	Controls n (%)	P-value	OR (95% CI)
D25	Leiomyoma of uterus	2866 (48.0)	9944 (17.4)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	5.0 (4.9-5.1)
D27	Benign neoplasm of ovary	1273 (21.3)	3712 (6.5)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	4.0 (3.9-4.0)
N83	Noninflammatory disorders of ovary, fallopian tube and broad ligament	1868 (31.3)	6845 (12.0)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.5 (3.4-3.5)
N84	Polyp of corpus uteri	1743 (29.2)	5727 (10.0)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.8 (3.8-3.9)
N92	Excessive, frequent and irregular menstruation	3083 (51.6)	13463 (23.6)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.6 (3.5-3.6)
N97	Female infertility	1622 (27.2)	4860 (8.5)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	4.7 (4.6-4.7)
Z54	Convalescence	2105 (35.2)	9057 (15.9)	6.9×10^{-285}	2.9 (2.9-3.0)
Z31	Procreative management	790 (13.2)	1908 (3.3)	1.1×10^{-274}	5.2 (5.1-5.2)
N85	Other noninflammatory disorders of uterus, except cervix	1030 (17.2)	3071 (5.4)	1.4×10^{-255}	3.9 (3.8-3.9)
N73	Other female pelvic inflammatory diseases	545 (9.1)	1069 (1.9)	1.8×10^{-200}	5.2 (5.1-5.3)
N70	Salpingitis and oophoritis	1064 (17.8)	3813 (6.7)	4.1×10^{-191}	3.1 (3.0-3.2)
N94	Pain and other conditions associated with female genital organs and menstrual cycle	1348 (22.6)	7103 (12.4)	8.9×10^{-137}	2.4 (2.3-2.4)
N72	Inflammatory disease of cervix uteri	1958 (32.8)	10975 (19.2)	5.8×10^{-134}	2.1 (2.0-2.1)
N76	Other inflammation of vagina and vulva	3135 (52.5)	21008 (36.8)	2.7×10^{-124}	1.9 (1.9-2.0)
Z12	Special screening examination for neoplasms	3702 (62.0)	26639 (46.6)	1.1×10^{-115}	1.9 (1.8-2.0)

N95	Menopausal and other perimenopausal disorders	1926 (32.3)	13930 (24.4)	8.1×10^{-107}	2.1 (2.0-2.1)
D50	Iron deficiency anaemia	2142 (35.9)	13266 (23.2)	5.4×10^{-106}	1.9 (1.8-1.9)
R10	Abdominal and pelvic pain	2859 (47.9)	19910 (34.9)	6.4×10^{-88}	1.7 (1.7-1.8)
B37	Candidiasis	3003 (50.3)	21482 (37.6)	4.5×10^{-87}	1.7 (1.7-1.8)
D39	Neoplasm of uncertain or unknown behaviour of female genital organs	243 (4.1)	601 (1.1)	5.1×10^{-82}	4.6 (4.4-4.7)

645 OR, odds ratio

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648 Table III. The list of 20 most significant comorbidities of IBS cases compared with controls.

ICD-10 code	Comorbidity	IBS n (%)	Controls n (%)	P-value	OR (95% CI)
E73	Lactose intolerance	1047 (11.3)	877 (1.6)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	8.5 (8.4-8.6)
I84	Hemorrhoids	3159 (34.1)	8532 (15.2)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	2.7 (2.7-2.8)
K21	Gastro-oesophageal reflux disease	4331 (46.7)	11975 (21.3)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.0 (3.0-3.1)
K29	Gastritis and duodenitis	5149 (55.6)	14093 (25.1)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.6 (3.6-3.7)
K30	Functional dyspepsia	3498 (37.8)	8288 (14.8)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.4 (3.4-3.5)
K59	Diverticular disease of intestine	3313 (35.8)	6417 (11.4)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	4.3 (4.3-4.4)
R10	Abdominal and pelvic pain	5621 (60.7)	19522 (34.8)	$<1 \times 10^{-315}$	3.1 (3.1-3.2)
F41	Other anxiety disorders	3322 (35.9)	11102 (19.8)	9.2×10^{-233}	2.2 (2.2-2.3)
F45	Somatoform disorders	2844 (30.7)	9256 (16.5)	5.4×10^{-232}	2.3 (2.3-2.4)
K57	Paralytic ileus and intestinal obstruction without hernia	931 (10.0)	1126 (2.0)	6.6×10^{-230}	4.8 (4.7-4.9)
J30	Vasomotor and allergic rhinitis	3841 (41.5)	15492 (27.6)	3.3×10^{-182}	2.0 (1.9-2.0)
F32	Depressive episode	3720 (40.1)	13786 (24.5)	1.7×10^{-181}	2.0 (1.9-2.0)
G44	Other headache syndromes	2857 (30.8)	10349 (18.4)	2.2×10^{-177}	2.1 (2.0-2.1)
N30	Urethritis and urethral syndrome	5423 (58.5)	24045 (42.8)	3.9×10^{-173}	1.9 (1.9-1.9)
M54	Dorsalgia	7144 (77.1)	33487 (59.6)	5.0×10^{-166}	2.1 (2.0-2.2)
J31	Chronic rhinitis, nasopharyngitis and pharyngitis	2071 (22.4)	6376 (11.4)	1.6×10^{-162}	2.2 (2.1-2.2)
N95	Menopausal and other perimenopausal disorders	3946 (42.6)	13623 (24.3)	5.8×10^{-157}	2.1 (2.1-2.2)
K52	Ulcerative colitis	633 (6.8)	999 (1.8)	2.8×10^{-151}	4.0 (3.9-4.1)
D12	Benign neoplasm of colon, rectum, anus and anal canal	602 (6.5)	753 (1.3)	8.0×10^{-143}	4.3 (4.2-4.4)

Z03	Encounter for medical observation for suspected diseases and conditions ruled out	7510 (81.0)	39015 (69.5)	5.0×10^{-142}	2.1 (2.0-2.1)
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649 IBS, irritable bowel syndrome; OR, odds ratio

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651 Table IV. The list of 20 most significant comorbidities of women with both endometriosis and IBS
 652 (cases) compared with controls.

ICD-10 code	Comorbidity	Cases n (%)	Controls n (%)	P-value	OR (95% CI)
D25	Leiomyoma of uterus	476 (49.3)	10168 (17.4)	9.4×10^{-122}	4.8 (4.7-4.9)
E73	Lactose intolerance	135 (14.0)	920 (1.6)	1.6×10^{-121}	10.3 (10.1-10.5)
N92	Excessive, frequent and irregular menstruation	561 (58.1)	13753 (23.5)	9.6×10^{-118}	4.6 (4.5-4.8)
R10	Abdominal and pelvic pain	724 (74.9)	20444 (34.9)	9.2×10^{-117}	5.6 (5.5-5.8)
K21	Gastro-oesophageal reflux disease	525 (54.3)	12546 (21.4)	1.5×10^{-111}	4.4 (4.3-4.5)
K59	Other functional intestinal disorders	362 (37.5)	6721 (11.5)	3.2×10^{-109}	4.5 (4.4-4.7)
K29	Gastritis and duodenitis	574 (59.4)	14713 (25.1)	1.7×10^{-100}	4.2 (4.1-4.4)
N83	Noninflammatory disorders of ovary, fallopian tube and broad ligament	352 (36.4)	6996 (11.9)	1.5×10^{-99}	4.3 (4.2-4.4)
K30	Functional dyspepsia	400 (41.4)	8718 (14.9)	7.2×10^{-98}	4.0 (3.9-4.2)
N94	Pain and other conditions associated with female genital organs and menstrual cycle	328 (34.0)	7270 (12.4)	3.6×10^{-92}	4.3 (4.2-4.5)
I84	Hemorrhoids	403 (41.7)	8922 (15.2)	1.9×10^{-91}	3.9 (3.7-4.0)
N84	Polyp of corpus uteri	300 (31.1)	5853 (10.0)	2.0×10^{-84}	4.0 (3.9-4.2)
N70	Salpingitis and oophoritis	238 (24.6)	3892 (6.6)	1.4×10^{-82}	4.4 (4.3-4.6)
Z54	Convalescence	383 (39.6)	9271 (15.8)	9.6×10^{-77}	3.5 (3.3-3.6)
D27	Benign neoplasm of ovary	210 (21.7)	3798 (6.5)	2.5×10^{-64}	3.9 (3.7-4.0)
N95	Menopausal and other perimenopausal disorders	434 (44.9)	14246 (24.3)	1.4×10^{-60}	3.3 (3.1-3.4)
N85	Other noninflammatory disorders of uterus, except cervix	183 (18.9)	3142 (5.4)	5.1×10^{-60}	4.0 (3.8-4.2)

N73	Other female pelvic inflammatory diseases	101 (10.5)	1095 (1.9)	9.2×10^{-57}	5.8 (5.5-6.0)
N97	Female infertility	215 (22.3)	4966 (8.5)	8.3×10^{-55}	3.5 (3.3-3.7)
N60	Benign mammary dysplasia	298 (30.8)	7312 (12.5)	4.3×10^{-54}	3.0 (2.9-3.2)

653 IBS, irritable bowel syndrome; OR, odds ratio

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656 **Figures**

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658 **Figure 1.** Results for associated diagnoses analysis for endometriosis (top), IBS (middle) and

659 both diagnosis (bottom). Each triangle in the plot represents one ICD-10 code, which have

660 been colored according to chapter. IBS, irritable bowel syndrome

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662

663 **Supplementary material**

664 **Supplementary Figure S1.** A diagram showing the formation of study groups. N80 –
665 endometriosis, K58 – irritable bowel syndrome

666 **Supplementary Figure S2.** Frequency of selected obstetric diagnoses in endometriosis and
667 controls. O20, Haemorrhage in early pregnancy; O82, Single delivery by caesarean section;
668 O02, Other abnormal products of conception; O34, Maternal care for known or suspected
669 abnormality of pelvic organs; O03, Spontaneous abortion; O00, Ectopic pregnancy; O21,
670 Excessive vomiting in pregnancy; O60, Preterm labour and delivery; O30, Multiple gestation;
671 O84, Multiple delivery; O44, Placenta previa

672 **Supplementary Figure S3.** The numbers of unique and common endometriosis- and IBS-
673 related ICD-10 diagnosis codes. The figure is created using Venny 2.1 (Oliveros, J.C. (2007-
674 2015) Venny. An interactive tool for comparing lists with Venn's diagrams.
675 <https://bioinfogp.cnb.csic.es/tools/venny/index.html>). IBS, irritable bowel syndrome

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677 **Supplementary Table SI.** The comorbidities of endometriosis in the female cohort of the
678 EstBB, excluding relatives.

679 **Supplementary Table SII.** The comorbidities of irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) in the
680 female cohort of the EstBB, excluding relatives.

681 **Supplementary Table SIII.** The comorbidities of endometriosis and irritable bowel
682 syndrome in the female cohort of the EstBB, excluding relatives.

683 **Supplementary Table IV.** Unique and common endometriosis- and IBS-related ICD-10
684 diagnosis codes.

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